

Ideal Gas Entropy and the Question of Macrostates

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. July 1, 2026

Entropy is defined as $-k$ multiplied by the \ln of the number of macrostates, but it may seem unclear as to what should be considered to be proper macrostates for thermodynamic entropy. Thermodynamic entropy is that which is found in the first law of thermodynamics: $dE = T dS - PdV$. Here we try to examine how the notion of dS arises in the first place and how it may be linked with certain energy related macrostates.

We note that given the experimental result $PV=NT$ and the definition of pressure $= 1/V \langle \frac{1}{3} mv^2 \rangle$, one may directly obtain: $E = 3/2 NT$ without knowing $p(ei)$. Furthermore $dE = E d \ln(E) = kT d \ln(E \text{ power } 3N/2)$. If one notes that microstates are counted by points in momentum space (x space is dealt with separately), then E_{total} power $3N/2$ is the volume of a sphere in momentum (or velocity for m constant) and is proportional to the number of momentum states which is what one counts (together with x space states). In other words, the ideal gas law was almost fully known through the work of Boyle in the 1660s (and fully known by 1834 (3)) and at this time, the notion of entropy as the $-k \ln(\text{number of momentum states})$ could have been developed without Boltzmann's work, we argue. Formally, the full expression for the number of momentum states was given by Sackur and Tetrode (1) after Boltzmann's result, but the main idea of a volume in $3N$ momentum space still holds. The volume part of the number of states is $V \text{ power } N / N!$ If one deals with identical particles. We suggest that the ideal gas law: $dE = 0 = T dS - P dV$ follows whether one includes the $1/N!$ identical particle factor or not. Obtaining entropy through its link to energy and the ideal gas law indicates that the macrostates should be linked with energy and work. It is not the case that every identifiable macrostate should be counted, at least in the thermodynamic picture. It also seems that one may include states that are not linked strictly with energy and momentum if one wishes simply to create a math function $-k \ln(\text{all possible states})$ as a kind of information entropy.

The Notion of Entropy

It seems that entropy was introduced in the 1850s by Clausius and was not immediately given the interpretation of $-k \ln(\text{number of states})$. This would come later with Boltzmann. We suggest, however, that given the ideal gas law, known in 1834 (3):

$$PV = NkT \quad ((1))$$

one may obtain the first law of thermodynamics:

$$dE = TdS - PdV \quad ((2))$$

together with:

$$S = -k \ln(\text{number of momentum states}) \quad ((3))$$

Boyle's law:

$$P_1V_1 = P_2V_2 \quad ((4))$$

was already known in the 1660s and one may readily define:

$$PV = N \text{ function}(T) \quad ((5))$$

It was not until 1843, however, that a full expression for the ideal law was proposed (3). At this time, we argue that it would have been possible to have defined entropy as $-k \ln(\text{number of momentum states})$. We describe our reasoning which does not make use of Boltzmann's transport equation.

Entropy as $-k \ln(\text{number of states})$

Entropy (without its form as $-k \ln(\text{number of states})$) was introduced by Clausius in the 1860s and in the later 1800s Boltzmann, using his transport equation, defined it as

$$-k \ln(\text{number of states}) \quad ((6))$$

We suggest that one may reach this conclusion ((6)) without use of a transport equation. The key idea is to use the number of states as being given by the volume of a sphere in $3N$ momentum space, something that Sackur and Tetrode did (1) after Boltzmann developed ((6)).

We write:

$$dE = E d \ln(E) \quad ((7))$$

Then:

$$dE = \frac{3}{2} NkT \ln(E) = Tk \ln(E^{\text{power } 3/2 N}) \quad ((8))$$

Nonrelativistically, E behaves as momentum squared and so a radius in $3N$ momentum space changes as $E^{\text{power } 1/2}$ and the volume in momentum space as:

$$E^{\text{power } 3N/2} \quad ((9))$$

Thus, using the property

$$A \ln(b) = \ln(b^{\text{power } A}) \quad ((10))$$

one obtains the notion that dE is linked to a change in the \ln of the number of states in $3N$ momentum space. We suggest that this gives a natural reason for introducing the \ln of the number of states. In statistical mechanics, it is sometimes suggested that one should introduce

In of the number of states because the number of states is too large a number to deal with conveniently. Our use of the \ln is direct. Given that one has states in momentum space, one may introduce states in x -space, i.e.

$$V \text{ power } N / N! \quad ((11))$$

Here we include $1/N!$ To deal with identical particles, but this factor is not needed to reproduce the ideal gas law:

$$dE = 0 = -kT d \ln(V \text{ power } N) - PdV \quad ((13))$$

As a result, we suggest that ideas about entropy as $-k \ln(\text{number of states})$ seem to follow quite directly for an ideal gas from the ideal gas law $PV = NkT$.

The Question of What is a Macrostate

One may define macrostates in many different way based on what properties of particles one wishes to include. Using more properties leads to more macrostates and this may be fine if one wishes to capture information about a system. The thermodynamic entropy = $-k \ln(\text{number of } V \text{ and momentum states})$, however, deals with specific momentum-spatial states linked to changes in energy and $PV=NkT$. As a result, in the case of thermodynamic entropy one cannot simply count any macrostate that one wishes, even if there are technically different physical states.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that one may obtain $E=3/2 NkT$ and $S = -k \ln(\text{number of momentum states} * \text{number of } V \text{ states} * \text{constant})$ directly from the ideal gas law $PV=NkT$ which was fully discovered in 1834 even though $PV= N \text{ function}(T)$ was known in the 1660s. In particular, we use: $dE = E d \ln(E)$, i.e. make use of a property of the \ln which is not $\ln(ab)=\ln(a)+\ln(b)$, but rather $a \ln(b) = \ln(b \text{ power } a)$. This property, together with a $3N$ sphere in momentum space yield the notion of entropy and immediately equate it to $-k \ln(\text{number of momentum states})$ i.e. $dE = 3/2 N kT \ln(E) = kT \ln(E \text{ power } 3N/2)$. Here E is momentum squared (nonrelativistically) and so the radius in momentum space behaves as $E \text{ power } 1/2$ and the volume as $4*3/14/3 E \text{ power } 3N/2$. If one considers $-PdV$ as possibly changing E and spatial $\ln(\text{number spatial states})$ then one has $\ln(V \text{ power } N)$. At this point, one does not need to worry about identical particles.

Formally, the above ideas were developed fully by Sackur and Tetrode (1) using the form $S = -k \ln(\text{number of states})$ from Boltzmann, but we suggest that one may obtain the idea of entropy as $\ln(\text{number of states})$ without Boltzmann's definition and transport equation as done above. Furthermore, the above approach gives a sense of what macrostates one should include for thermodynamic entropy, we argue.

References

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